

Competency Level of Grade Six Teachers Based on Performance Evaluation Scorecard in Relation to Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP) Result

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Abstract

The study identified the competency level of grade six teachers based on performance evaluation scored and its relation to pupil's Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP) result. The study was descriptive-correlational in nature. The statistical tools used were the following: percentage, weighted mean μ , mean, spearman rank correlation coefficient, and Point-Biserial Correlation. The study found out that majority of the grade six teachers was female who are either young or old. Most of them have MA units and have been teaching for at least a year to ten years. The study revealed that majority of the grade six teachers were in the outstanding level based on their performance evaluation scorecard. The study also indicated that majority of the grade six pupils performed at the "beginning" level based on their DUTP result. The study also indicated that there is a low/slight relationship between the grade six teachers' competency level based on the performance evaluation scored and their pupil's Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP) result. However, Teachers' profile has a negligible relationship to their levels of competence.

Keywords: *Competency Level, Performance Evaluation Scorecard, Division Unified Testing Program*

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the many commitments of the Department of Education is to provide a quality system of public education. It provides schools with teachers who are able to help students develop their abilities, attitudes and skills for them to function effectively in an environment that is constantly changing. Having this aim, Department of Education established a set of Competency-Based Standards for Teachers Performance (Corpuz & Lucas, 2011). Clearly, this calls for teachers that possess salient characters and skills in order to carry out a satisfactory performance of their roles and responsibilities as facilitators of learning. It is imperative that the teacher is one of the key elements in a learning environment. If the teacher does his/her job wholeheartedly or not that the pupils' performance reflects that of the teacher.

The teacher's performance is important because the learning of the pupils greatly depend on how the teacher delivered the lessons. As a facilitator of learning he/she creates a learning environment suitable for diverse learners. A teacher should be able to cater to the needs of the pupils using any strategy or method that best fits their learning style. He or she should possess qualities that are needed in teaching. If the teacher has a good performance, pupils are assured to

perform well. She/he is able to produce pupils that are well prepared and skillful, and ready to take the next challenge.

The researcher chose this study in order to know if the teachers' rate/performance in their Performance Evaluation Scorecard (PES) affects their pupils DUTP results.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research used the descriptive survey since it focused at the present condition and the purpose is to find new truth. It used correlation since it determined the relationship between the competency level of grade six teachers which is the primary independent variable, the teachers' profile which is the secondary independent variable and the pupil's DUTP result which is the dependent variable.

Research Environment

The place of the study was at Bayawan City or known as the "Character City". Bayawan became a chartered city in December 2000. It boasts its distinction as a "Character City" (International Association of Character Cities) and a pioneer "Healthy City" (DOH certified) in the Philippines. Recently, the Asian Institute of Management recognized the city as "one of the Top 10 Best Cities to Live In in the Philippines (Small Cities Category)" under its Competitive Cities Survey 2007. It is the only city in the Southern part of Negros Oriental. It is composed of 28 Barangays. Each barangay has secondary, elementary and primary schools. (Bayawan History). The city has its own division, consisting of three districts the East, West and Basay District.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 41 Grade VI Teachers of the Public Elementary Schools in the East and West Districts of Bayawan City Division.

Research Instruments

This research made use of a questionnaire to only elicit profile information from the Grade Six teachers. This study further made use of the available data from the teachers' Performance Evaluation Scorecard (PES) which is a yearly evaluation for teachers as a tool in identifying their level of competency, and the average rate of the class performance in the Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP).

Research Procedure

A written request was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent asking permission to allow the researcher to conduct a study within her jurisdiction. Once the request was approved, the principal of the different schools were given a copy of the approved letter. Next, the researcher asked for a copy of the PES of the selected Grade Six teachers and the average rate of the class performance in the Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP). The data were tabulated and sent to the statistician for the statistical treatment.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

Table 1. *Age Profile of the Teachers*

Age	Frequency	Percent
25 – 34	25	36.23
35 – 44	19	27.54
45 and above	25	36.23
Total	69	100.00

Table 1 shows the profile of the grade six teachers in terms of age. It can be gleaned from the data that, the lowest and the highest bracket of age of grade six teachers have equal percentage. This means that there is the same frequency of early adults and late adults in the East and West Districts of Bayawan City Division.

Table 2. *Sex Profile of the Teachers*

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	56	81.16
Male	13	18.84
Total	69	100.00

Table 2 presents the distribution of grade six teachers by sex groups. In this study, majority of the teacher respondents are female.

The data show that teaching is mostly by a female domain. This can be substantiated by the fact that undeniably, nationwide, there are more female teachers than male teachers in all levels of education. Likewise, the current study concurs with the study of Milan and Ojastro wherein they declared that there are fewer male teachers than female teachers in the Division of Dumaguete City.

According to Brown (2016), people think that primary school teachers should be female. Females tend to have more of a liking for the little kids and have a temperament suited to working with them. Lee (2016) added that women have developed and gained more patience in dealing with younger children. Elementary school is more about nurturing social skills rather than focusing academically on “certain subjects,” which is what men are better at teaching.

The study of Amores, Divinagracia, and Nilemaas cited by (Elloremo 2015) disclosed that there are more women than men in the teaching profession.

Table 3. *Educational Qualifications of the Teachers*

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	10	14.49
With MA Units	50	72.46
With MA	7	10.15
With Doctoral Units	2	2.90
Total	69	100.00

Table 3 shows that majority of the grade six teachers have shown professional advancement evident in their units obtained in the Master of Arts Program. A smaller percentage of the respondents are Full-Fledged MA holders and the smallest percentage of the respondents has doctoral units.

According to Gregorio, it is not sufficient to be a graduate of a normal school or college. Like the pupils, teachers must grow and this growth must be both professional and personal. Moreover, the Department of Education has encouraged all of its teachers to seek higher academic qualifications.

Table 4. *Length of Teaching Experience*

Number of Years	Frequency	Percent
1 – 10	33	47.83
11 – 20	18	26.09
21 and above	18	26.09
Total	69	100.00

Reflected in Table 4 is the profile of teachers in terms of length of teaching experience. It indicates that the biggest percentage of grade six teachers is clustered on the lower bracket in terms of teaching experience.

The data indicate that there is a greater number of relatively new grade six teachers than the number of experienced teachers in the East and West districts of Bayawan City Division.

According to Great Schools (2014), schools should have a balance of beginning and experienced teachers. Teachers with more years of experience have provided stability for a school and mentored new teachers while beginning teachers have brought enthusiasm and fresh ideas to the classroom. Experienced teachers have been known to possess deeper understanding about educational practices, exhibit high level of self-monitoring skills, examine problems and identify problems quickly and fairly accurately, and process meaningful patterns within their subject areas. Teachers with more years of experience have been more capable of comprehending and describing classroom occurrences and have been able to interpret students' behavior and offer possible solutions for problematic situations. (Carter, 1988; Sabers, Cushing, & Berliner, 1991).

Table 5. *Competency Level of the Grade Teachers Based on the Performance Evaluation Scorecard*

Competency Level Scale	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percent
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding	51	73.91
3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory	18	26.09
Total		69	100.00

Shown in table 5 is the performance of teachers on the Performance Evaluation Scorecard. It indicates that majority of the grade six teachers were in the outstanding level. Only a few are in the Very Satisfactory level.

This shows that teachers have a very good performance in their Performance Evaluation Scorecard. Most of them were able to comply with all the requirements needed in the said evaluation.

Table 6. *Performance of Grade Six Pupils Based on the DUTP Results*

Rating	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percent
80% - 84%	Approaching Proficiency	2	2.90
75% - 79%	Developing	2	2.90
Below 75%	Beginning	65	94.20
Total		69	100.00

Average: 63.97% Beginning

Table 6 indicates the frequency distribution of the grade six pupils' performance based on DUTP results. It shows that majority of the grade six pupils are in the "beginning" level in terms of their academic performance based on their DUTP result. This indicates that pupils' performance in their DUTP is low. DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012 defines this level as "The pupil at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding."

This conforms to the study of Igos (2014) where she revealed that the overall Science DUTP performance of the students is in "Beginning" level.

Table 7. *Relationship between the Teachers' Level of Competency and Their Pupils' DUTP Results*

Variables	Computed r_s	Coefficient of Determination	Degree of Relationship
Teachers' Level of Competency and Pupils' DUTP Results	0.223	4.97%	Low/Slight

The data illustrate that the computed value of r_s is 0.223 with a verbal equivalent of low or slight relationship. The coefficient of determination (0.0497) signifies that 4.97% of the variance in DUTP results of the pupils is explained by the teachers' level of competency. This attribution is considered to be low. The remaining percentage (95.03%) is due to other factors not included in this study.

Teacher competence affects pupils' performance only to a low or slight extent. These findings are supported by the study of Ellorema which revealed that teachers' level of competency has a relationship with pupils' NAT Result or performance.

Table 8. *Relationship between the Teachers' Profile and Their Level of Competency*

Variables Being Paired with Teachers' Level of Competency	Computed r	Degree of Relationship
Sex	$r_{pbi}=0.167$	Negligible
Educational Qualifications	$r_s = 0.177$	Negligible
Length of Teaching Experience	$r_s = 0.039$	Negligible

The data indicate that the profile of the teachers (sex, educational qualifications and length of teaching experience) has a negligible relationship with their level of competence. This indicates that male and female teachers have the same level of competency. Likewise, teachers with bachelor's degree only or with MA units/degrees have the same performance in school. Furthermore, the novice teachers and the seasoned ones reveal the same level of competency.

The data is contradicting with the study of Hamdan (2010) from which he stated that all the teachers were competent and there existed a significant relationship of gender and teaching experience. However, it is similar with the academic qualification which had no significant influence on their teaching competence.

Shanavaz (2007) also confirmed in his study that teachers' competency is not related by length of experiences.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based upon the findings listed above, the following conclusions drawn:

1. Majority of the respondents were female teachers who may be either in the early adulthood or late adulthood in terms of age; who have MA units, and have been teaching for at least a year to 10 years.
2. The competency level of grade six teachers based on the performance evaluation score card is in the outstanding level.
3. The performance of the majority of grade six pupils based on the DUTP result is in the "Beginning" level.

4. There is a low/slight relationship between the Grade six teachers' level of competency and their pupils' DUTP result.
5. The profile of the grade six teachers has a negligible relationship between their levels of competency based on the performance evaluation scorecard.

In general, teachers have surpassed the expectations set by the PES standards as revealed by their "outstanding" performance. In the contrary, however, their pupils performed only at the "beginning" level. Furthermore, the teachers' PES results had a slight relationship to the pupils' DUTP result. Moreover, there were not enough evidences established to prove a relationship between the teachers' profile and their PES results.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Interestingly, this study revealed that teachers performed "outstandingly" based on their PES but their pupils were only at the "beginning" level as revealed by their DUTP result. From these findings, the following recommendations are considered by the researcher.

1. The DepEd administration reexamines the criteria and qualifications in the PES as to its responsiveness to pupils' academic needs. Further, it is recommended that DepEd continue to provide quality faculty development programs to uplift the status of all teachers especially those who did not make it to the "outstanding" level.
2. Teachers consider to reevaluate their pedagogical methods so as to respond to the academic needs of the pupils. Moreover, teachers are recommended to consider factors other than teacher factors that could have possibly affected the academic performance of the pupils.
3. The pupils, their parents, and the people in the community are recommended to be cognizant with the factors that could contribute to the academic success of the learners. This recommendation is considered given that in the factors affecting pupils' performance, 95.03% is attributed to other factors aside from the PES performance factor of the teacher.

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